

The Holy Apostles Community, Ori-Oke Iwamimo

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The Holy Apostles Community, Ori-Oke Iwamimo was originally called "The Maran Apostles community." It was known by this nomenclature for a little over two decades until it changed to its current name in 1972. Unlike the other dominant theocratic communities in Ilajeland which were started on virgin lands, Ori-Oke Iwamimo had been established by the father of Prophet Wilson Etan Ikudehinbu, the first leader of this theocratic community. Ikudehinbu was a former member of the Ayetoro theocratic community. He left Ayetoro due to some irreconcilable differences between himself and the monarch of Ayetoro in late 1950. By this time, the idea of theocratic settlements was becoming fashionable in Ilajeland due to the initial successes recorded by Ayetoro and Ugbonla. Ikudehinbu was therefore allowed to settle in Ori-Oke iwamimo and to propagate his faith in the manner he deemed fit. By 1951, the community became a theocratic settlement and was led by Ikudehinbu until August 2002 when he passed on. His son, Prophet Alebiosu has led the community since 2004. This was after the fierce leadership tussle which engulfed the community after Ikudehinbu's demise had been apprehended. Ori-Oke Iwamimo community has been quite vibrant in their faith. Their mode of worship is like that found in other theocratic communities in Ilajeland, especially that of Ayetoro. However, they have also developed and maintained other distinct practices which stand them apart from their peers in the Ilaje littoral. Significant among their distinct practices maintained during the lifetime of the first Oba (monarch) is the special annual worship which held at the seashore beside the community church. During the performance of this ritual, the Oba invoked the sea. It is believed in the community that by some uncommon powers he causes the wave to rise and flood parts of the settlement. The Oba stands with his back to the sea while the congregation faces him. As the ritual gets under way, a big bowl is placed on a table in the glare of the people. When the water floods the arena, some of it is retained in the bowl. Special interventions are reported when the water leaps on the congregation. Before the ritual is ended, the water trapped in the bowl is sprinkled on the congregants. It is widely held in the community that the water sprinkled on participants is efficacious in bringing protection, good luck, healing and other favours to the congregants. Ori-Oke Iwamimo joins Ayetoro, Ugbonla and Zion Pepe to complete the list of the four most prosperous theocratic communities in Ilajeland. By a series of deliberate actions, the community lobbied the government of the Western State of Nigeria in the late 1960s and early 1970s to request the dredging of the canal which connects it and other villages to the Alape river. This was after it had previously conducted a manual dredging of the same canal with some successes. Ori-Oke Iwamimo remains the only theocratic community among the four most prominent in Ilajeland which has not adopted the use of prayer garments.

Date Range: 1950 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Ori-Oke Iwamimo, Ilaje local government area of Ondo State, Nigeria

Region tags: Africa, Nigeria, Nigeria, Southwest Nigeria, Ilajeland

Ori-Oke iwamimo theocratic community is located in Ilajeland on the far eastern flank of Yorubaland. It is a coastal community bounded by the Atlantic Ocean and a network of rivers and canals. Transportation in

and around the community is facilitated by canoes and boats.

Status of Participants:

- ✓ Elite
- ✓ Religious Specialists
- ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources

Print sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Barrett, R. Stanley, *Two Villages on Stilts: Economic and Family Change in Nigeria* (New York: Chandler Publishing Company, 1974)
- Source 2: Barrett, R. Stanley, *The Rise and Fall of an African Utopia: A Wealthy Theocracy in Comparative Perspective* (Ontario: Wilfrid Laurier University Press, 1977)
- Source 1: Barrett, R. Stanley, *The Rise and Fall of an African Utopia: A Wealthy Theocracy in Comparative Perspective* (Ontario: Wilfrid Laurier University Press, 1977)

Relevant online primary textual corpora (original languages and/or translations):

- Source 1 URL: <https://www.africanportal.net/ABO/BibeliAtoka/>

General Variables

Membership/Group Interactions

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– Yes

Notes: Other religious groups are in contact with Ori-Oke Iwamimo theocratic community. The community relates well with other theocratic settlements around them and share in the joy of their celebrations and religious programmes.

Is the cultural contact competitive:

– No

Notes: The Holy Apostles Community, Ori-Oke Iwamimo is one of the four most dominant Aladura Christian groups in Ilajeland, southwest, Nigeria. It has its roots in the Cherubim and Seraphim movement which started in Lagos in 1925. It separated from the Holy Apostles community, Ayetoro at about 1950. The core of its religious beliefs are similar to those of other theocratic communities in Ilajeland. Though the church interacts with other theocratic settlements in Ilajeland, it has some distinct features which sets it apart from other religious settlements in its immediate environment. The community is firm in its dogma and traditions such that its doctrines are not easily eroded by other Christian groups it interacts with.

Is the cultural contact accommodating/pluralistic:

– No

Notes: The church accepts invitations to religious programmes organised by other Christian

groups around it. It is selective in its choice of churches it invites to her celebrations. It is never in a hurry to inculcate practices of other Christian communities around it. Ori-Oke Iwamimo maintains cultural contact only with Christian communities it holds as professing similar articles of faith with it. It is unfriendly with those who follow the autochthonous traditional religious beliefs.

↳ Is the cultural contact neutral:

– No

Notes: Ori-Oke Iwamimo's cultural contact cannot be described as neutral. The church is quite clear about its beliefs, doctrines and dogma. It embraces and interacts freely with those Christian communities it holds as professing similar faith with them but distances itself from any religious group considered as holding faith viewed to be at variance with theirs.

↳ Is there violent conflict (within sample region):

– No

Notes: Although a nucleus of members of Ori-Oke Iwamimo left Ayetoro to establish this community, they do not as a distinct group share the unique history of Ayetoro which was involved in a running battle with the traditional authority in Ilajeland before and shortly after its founding. There has been no violent conflicts recorded between this community and others around them. However, there are unofficial reports of some healthy competitions and superiority contests between Ori-Oke Iwamimo and some other theocratic communities around them in their short history.

↳ Is there violent conflict (with groups outside the sample region):

– No

Notes: There have been no reports of violent conflicts between the community and groups outside the sample region.

Does the religious group have a general process/system for assigning religious affiliation:

– Yes

↳ Assigned at birth (membership is default for this society):

– Yes

Notes: A certain degree of membership-satisfaction is ascribed to children born to members of the Ori-Oke Iwamimo community. These individuals would however be expected to consolidate on their membership once they become adults and are able to decide on their future.

↳ Assigned by personal choice:

– Yes

Notes: Membership of Ori-Oke Iwamimo is assigned by personal choice of individuals willing to be so identified.

↳ Assigned by class:

– No

Notes: There are no class considerations for those willing to become members of the Ori-Oke Iwamimo theocratic community.

↳ Assigned at a specific age:

– No

Notes: There are no regulations regarding a specific age when people could be conferred with membership of the community. Generally, an adult could decide on the moment s/he becomes ready to publicly declare their readiness for membership of the community.

↳ Assigned by gender:

– No

Notes: There are no restrictions when considering individuals for Ori-Oke Iwamimo's membership on the basis of their gender.

↳ Assigned by participation in a particular ritual:

– Yes

Notes: In the past, when membership of theocratic communities in Ilajeland was extremely fashionable, ceremonies were held to induct members into the community. However, these ceremonies are seldom done as they seem to have been relaxed.

↳ Assigned by some other factor:

– No

Notes: No other factor except the free will of would-be members is necessary for conferring membership of Ori-Oke Iwamimo on people

Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members:

– No

Notes: Ori-Oke Iwamimo does not actively proselytize. In fact, it does not have a membership recruitment strategy as it relies on the convincing powers behind the activities of her prophets to draw people to the community.

Does the religion have official political support

– No

Notes: No official political support exists for Ori-Oke Iwamimo community. The people are however active politically and have been known to support politicians and voted candidates to office who were friendly to the community while holding political positions.

Is there a conception of apostasy in the religious group:

– No

Notes: The church has been consistent with her religious views and has continued to pursue their convictions quite strongly. There is however a record of some spiritual lull in the current generation of her membership compared to what is known of the generation which established the community. Most of the members keep their faith and membership of the community even if they are away from the village for years. There are no known records denunciation of faith by people who identify with the community.

Size and Structure

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– Estimated population, numeric: 3785

Notes: The 1991 National Population Census in Nigeria figures in Nigeria puts the Ori-Oke Iwamimo population at 3785. The most recent population census held in the country in 2006 has been disputed making the 1991 figures more acceptable. Although population changes have occurred as reflected in migration patterns, deaths and births etc, this figure gives an idea of the size of the community during the period when the census was conducted.

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (% of sample region population, numerical):

– Estimated population, percentage of sample region: 7.5

Notes: The total population of Ilajeland during the 1991 census was 50,188 persons. When Ori-Oke Iwamimo's population of 3785 is put as a percentage of the total Ilaje population, it places the community's population as 7.5% of the entire population of Ilajeland. This is significant given the fact that Ilajeland is made up of about 177 communities.

Nature of religious group [please select one]:

– Large religious group (with smaller religious groups not officially allowed but in practice tolerated)

Are there recognized leaders in the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Is there a hierarchy among these leaders:

– Yes

Notes: There is hierarchy among the leaders of the community. The monarch is the highest authority and is supported by a group of prophets and other administrators.

↳ A single leader of a local community:

– Yes

Notes: The monarch (Oba) is the recognised leader of the community. He is usually a

prophet and supported by other prophets and administrators who help pilot the affairs of the community.

↳ Multiple religious communities each with its own leader, no hierarchy among these leaders:

– No

Notes: Ori-Oke Iwamimo is a single community with its leaders. It however tried affiliating itself to Ayetoro around 1970. This did not quite work out. The community had to revert to its original structure after the unsuccessful merger attempt.

↳ "Regional" leaders who oversee one or more local leader(s) (e.g. bishops):

– No

Notes: The community does not operate the system of regional leadership as it did not actively operate branch system in the height of its spiritual success

↳ A single leader for the religious group that oversees all other leaders in the sample region:

– Yes

Notes: Though the community did not actively operate a branch system, the Oba oversees all other leaders within the community as authority flows from him.

↳ A council or group of leaders for the religious group that oversees all other leaders in the sample region:

– Yes

Notes: Through the authority of the Oba, committees and councils are inaugurated to oversee different activities and businesses of the community. These leaders report to the Oba for accountability.

↳ Estimate how many levels there are in the hierarchy of religious leadership:

– Number of levels [numeric value]: 3

Notes: There are about three identifiable levels of leadership in Ori-Oke Iwamimo. The Oba is the first level. This is followed by the leaders he commits tasks and assignments to for the overall coordination of the community. The members are the third and final level of religious leadership. They support the policies and directives of the Oba and their leaders and ensure the community continues to enjoy peace, progress and development.

↳ Are leaders believed to possess supernatural powers or qualities:

– Yes

↳ Powers are acquired by individual deeds carried out in past lives:

– No

Notes: Ori-Oke Iwamimo community does believe that powers are acquired by individual deeds carried out in past lives. The community holds that each individual has but one life to live. They do not hold the doctrine of reincarnation

↳ Powers are acquired by individual deeds carried out in the current life:

– Yes

Notes: The community holds that the more an individual lives right and continues to obey divine instructions the more they attain spiritual significance to operate in realms of the supernatural.

↳ Powers are inherited:

– No

Notes: The community does not believe that powers are inherited.

↳ Powers are culturally transmitted from a supernatural being:

– Yes

Notes: The community believes that the supernatural being bestows on each person what has been destined for them. Powers are therefore culturally transmitted from the supernatural being in the community.

↳ Powers are culturally transmitted from another human (e.g. teacher):

– No

Notes: No human being (teacher) transmits powers to people in the community. All power is conceived of as emanating from the supreme being in Ori-Oke Iwamimo.

↳ Powers are associated with leadership office they assume:

– Yes

Notes: In a sense, powers are associated with leadership offices in Ori-Oke Iwamimo. However, the charisma of individuals occupying an office also has a way of adding to or diminishing the powers which should be associated with some positions.

↳ Are religious leaders chosen:

– Yes

↳ A leader chooses his/her own replacement:

– No

Notes: There has been only one transition from the founding leader of the community to the reigning Oba since 1950 when the community was founded. However, the late Oba did not select his successor. One of his sons (not the eldest) is the current king. This is unlike the case usually in most traditional Yoruba communities where the first son

appears to have the right of first refusal to the throne or generally the properties of their late father. .

↳ A leader's retinue or ministers chooses the new leader:

– Yes

Notes: The ministers or leaders who worked with the first Oba (monarch) of Ori-Oke Iwamimo selected his son to succeed his father. There was a struggle for the throne at the time of investiture. In fact a part of the community stock with a prominent assistant of the first king but the majority of the leaders preferred the son of the founder to his assistant who also had an ambition for the position.

↳ Other leaders in the religious group choose that leader:

– No

Notes: Only leaders who were recognised by the first monarch and saddled with responsibilities of administering the community were involved in the selection of the current Oba.

↳ A political leader chooses the leader:

– No

Notes: No political leader has a role to play in the selection or choice of the leader of Ori-Oke Iwamimo

↳ Other members of the leader's congregation choose the leader:

– No

Notes: No other member of the leader's congregation choose a new leader for the community. The recognised leaders who have been involved in administering the community with the first Oba were involved in the selection process of the reigning Oba.

↳ All members of the religious group in the sample region participate in choosing the leader:

– No

Notes: Members of the religious group in Ori-Oke Iwamimo do not participate actively in choosing the leader. However, they express their opinions on the contenders to the throne and support members of the selection team who seem to favour their preferred candidate.

↳ Communication with supernatural power(s) believed to be part of the selection process:

– Yes

Notes: In Ori-Oke Iwamimo, communication with supernatural powers is believed to be part of the selection process. The leaders (prophets) who decide on the choice of a new

Oba are believed to engage in prayers and contemplation to ensure they pronounce the candidate the supernatural being chooses.

↳ Are leaders considered fallible:

– Yes

↳ Charges of fallibility made by a leader's own followers:

– No

Notes: Though leaders in Ori-Oke Iwamimo are considered to be fallible, their followers do not normally bring such charges against them.

↳ Charges of fallibility made by other leaders in the religious group:

– No

Notes: Leaders subordinate in rank to a superior do not normally accuse their superior of fallibility in Ori-Oke Iwamimo.

↳ Charges of fallibility made by a political ruler:

– No

Notes: There has not been a report or charge of fallibility brought against the leaders of Ori-Oke Iwamimo by any political leader in the past.

Scripture

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also “oral scriptures” (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– Yes

Notes: The religious group believes in the authority of the Holy Bible.

↳ Are they written:

– Yes

Notes: The Holy Bible is written

↳ Are they oral:

– No

Notes: The Holy Bible is not oral.

↳ Is there a story (or a set of stories) associated with the origin of scripture:

– Yes

Notes: Christians hold that the Holy Bible is the inspired word of the supreme God.

↳ Revealed by a high god:

– Yes

↳ Revealed by other supernatural being:

– No

Notes: The supreme high God is held as the source of the inspirations of the Holy Bible. However, the community holds that he delegated some other supernatural beings especially angels to reveal certain aspects of the scriptures to the individuals who received the divine messages at the time they were released to humanity.

↳ Inspired by high god:

– Yes

Notes: The high God is seen as the force behind the revelation of the Holy scriptures

↳ Inspired by other supernatural being:

– No

Notes: According to the community, no other supernatural being masterminded the revelation of the Holy Bible. They believe that only the supernatural supreme being did.

↳ Originated from divine or semi-divine human beings:

– No

Notes: No divine or semi divine human beings is believed on as the one from whom the Holy Bible originated.

↳ Originated from non-divine human being:

– No

Notes: Ori-Oke Iwamimo community does not believe that a non-divine human being masterminded the canonization of the Holy Bible.

↳ Are the scriptures alterable:

– No

Notes: The Holy Bible believed upon in Ori-Oke Iwamimo is not alterable

↳ Are there formal institutions (i.e. institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders) for interpreting the scriptures:

– No

Notes: The bible is not subject to any rigorous interpretation in the community. The religious leaders and prophets are inspired from time to time to speak to the congregation from portions of the bible as they are inspired.

↳ Is there a select group of people trained in transmitting the scriptures:

– No

Notes: The scriptures in use in the community has long being transmitted and translated to the Yoruba language which is spoken in the community.

↳ Is there a codified canon of scriptures:

– Yes

Notes: The Holy Bible in use in the community had been canonised as nothing can be taken from it or added to it.

Architecture, Geography

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– Yes

↳ In the average settlement, what percentage of area is taken up by all religious monuments:

– Percentage: 5

Notes: The space taken by the religious monument in the community is less than 5% of the community's land mass

↳ Size of largest single religious monument, square meters:

– Square meters: 1000

Notes: The church auditorium in the community occupies an area of about 1000 square meters

↳ Height of largest single religious monument, meters:

– Height, meters: 15

Notes: The height of the church auditorium is about 15 meters

↳ Size of average monument, square meters:

– Height, square meters: 10

Notes: The mausoleum of the demised first monarch of the community is about 10 square meters

↳ Height of average monument, meters:

– Height, meters: 12

Notes: The height of the mausoleum of the demised first monarch is about 12 meters

↳ In the largest settlement, what percentage of area is taken up by all religious monuments:

– Percentage of area: 5

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– Yes

↳ Tombs:

– Yes

Notes: The tomb (mausoleum) of the first monarch is located in front of the church. Members pray in the tomb and confirm they receive answers to the prayers they make in the tomb.

↳ Cemeteries:

– No

Notes: There are no cemeteries in the community.

↳ Temples:

– Yes

Notes: The community has only one church where all their religious meetings are held.

↳ Altars:

– Yes

Notes: There is only one recognised altar in the community church.

↳ Devotional markers:

– Yes

Notes: The altar of the church serves as a devotional marker for members of the community.

↳ Mass gathering point [plazas, courtyard, square. Places permanently demarcated using visible objects or structures]:

– No

Notes: There is no purpose built mass gathering point in the community except the church auditorium. However, depending on the number of people involved in a meeting outside religious gatherings groups meet at the residence of the monarch or at the community jetty.

↳ Other type of religious monumental architecture:

– Yes [specify]: The mausoleum of the first monarch is the only other monumental architecture in the community.

Is iconography present:

– No

Notes: Iconographies are not present in Ori-Oke iwamimo community.

Are there specific sites dedicated to sacred practice or considered sacred:

– Yes

Notes: The church auditorium and the mausoleum of the demised first king are considered as sacred places in the community

↳ Are sacred site oriented to environmental features:

"Environmental features" refers to features in the landscape, mountains, rivers, cardinal directions etc...

– Yes

Notes: The church auditorium is built close to the ocean shore in the community. A very significant annual religious programme held beside the church in the days of the first monarch when the ocean current is invoked to flood the arena where the congregants are gathers. The current was believed to bring healing and resolve several problems faced by the people in attendance.

Are pilgrimages present:

– Yes

Notes: People visited the community to see the spiritual interventions been done in the lives of the people by the prophets. Many people became members of the community through such visits.

↳ How strict is pilgrimage:

– Obligatory for some

Notes: Pilgrimage to Ori-Oke Iwamimo is obligatory for leaders in branches outside the community but optional to casual members

Beliefs

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer "no" only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body. Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– Yes

Notes: The spirit-body distinction is present in the community.

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as having qualitatively different powers or properties than other body parts:

– Yes

Notes: The community believes that the spirit-mind has qualitatively different powers or properties than the other body parts. It is held in the community that the spirit is the real essence of the human. When the spirit departs the body, then humans are said to have died.

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as non-material, ontologically distinct from body:

– Yes

Notes: Though the community holds that the spirit-mind is non-material, it nonetheless is the real and undying component of every human being.

↳ Other spirit-body relationship:

– Yes [specify]: The body remains on earth after the spirit departs from it. It decays and comes to its final end but the spirit outlives the body. It receives the rewards or punishment for the actions done in the body while it existed in the earthly realm.

Belief in afterlife:

– Yes

Notes: Ori-Oke Iwamimo believes in the afterlife

↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: The spatial location of the afterlife is described by the community.

↳ Afterlife in specified realm of space beyond this world:

– Yes

Notes: According to Ori-Oke Iwamimo theology, there are two distinct locations of the afterlife. Those who have obeyed divine instructions will inherit bliss in the afterlife. This afterlife would be somewhere in the sky while the evil folks would have their afterlife in a distressing place in the bowels of the earth

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined “above” space:

– Yes

Notes: This afterlife 'above' is for the good folks who lived a life of devotion and obedience to the supreme being. This space is however not vaguely described in the community's theology

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined "below" space:

– Yes

Notes: This afterlife 'below' is for the evil folks who lived a life of obedience to the supreme being. This space is however not vaguely described in the community's theology. The theology relating to this space is well developed and not ambiguous.

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined horizontal space:

– No

Notes: The afterlife in Ori-Oke Iwamimo is not in a horizontal space to the earth

↳ Afterlife located in "other" space:

– No

Notes: The afterlife in Ori-Oke Iwamimo theology is in two locations; viz: above and beneath. It is not in any "other" space.

Reincarnation in this world:

– No

Notes: The community does not hold the idea of a reincarnation in this world. They believe that it is appointed unto man to die once. After this death comes judgement.

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– No

Notes: There are no special treatments for adherent's corpses in Ori-Oke Iwamimo

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– No

Notes: There are no co-sacrifices present in tombs or burials in Ori-Oke Iwamimo

Are grave goods present:

– No

Notes: Grave goods are not present in Ori-Oke Iwamimo community. The dead are buried without any goods accompanying them. The community believes that every being came into the world without anything and each will return without any goods, servants, companion or properties

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

Notes: Formal burials are conducted in Ori-Oke Iwamimo. However, because it is a coastal community bounded by the Atlantic Ocean on its entire eastern flank, members are not interred in the community. Only two individuals have been buried in the community in its over seventy years history. The tombs of the first monarch and his brother stand in the community while every other member gets a burial

place in Ebute Ipore, a community further along on the way to the mainland.

↳ As cenotaphs:

– No

Notes: Cenotaphs are not erected in Ori-Oke Iwamimo

↳ In cemetery:

– No

Notes: Cemeteries are not present in Ori-Oke Iwamimo. Because of their extreme closeness to the ocean, they prefer to bury their dead in Ebute Ipore, a community further on the way to the mainland. They have an understanding with Ebute Ipore community to bury their dead.

↳ Family tomb-crypt:

– No

Notes: There are no family tombs in Ori-Oke Iwamimo

↳ Domestic (individuals interred beneath house, or in areas used for normal domestic activities):

– No

Notes: Members of Ori-Oke Iwamimo are not interred in the community.

↳ Other formal burial type:

– No

Notes: No other formal burial types are present in Ori-Oke Iwamimo.

Supernatural Beings

Are supernatural beings present:

– Yes

Notes: Supernatural beings are present in Ori-Oke Iwamimo theology

↳ A supreme high god is present:

– Yes

Notes: The existence of a supreme high god is central to Ori-Oke Iwamimo theology

↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic:

– Yes

Notes: The supreme high god is anthropomorphic in the theology of the community. They often speak of the high god as having human qualities and attributes.

↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity:

– Yes

Notes: The community has a well grounded theology regarding the location of the high god. They agree that their high god resides in the heavens above the sky

↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld):

– No

Notes: The community holds that their supreme high god lives in the sky and not the underworld.

↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god):

– No

Notes: Though they hold their monarch in high regards, the community however makes a distinction between him and the supreme high god. They believe that the supreme high god is no monarch with any mortal no matter how influential or powerful the mortal may be. The community holds that the supreme high god enables the monarch to perform all the great feats he does. They never make the mistake of equating the high god with the monarch or any other mortal.

↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:

– Yes

Notes: The community holds that the monarch like every other mortal is the manifestation or emanation of the high god.

↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites:

– No

Notes: The community makes no mistake about equating any mortal no matter their pedigree as a kin relation to the high god. The relationship that exists between humans and the high god in Ori-Oke Iwamimo is that humans emanate from the high god. Humans exist at the mercy of the high god. Humans are the creation of the high god and are also created in the image of the high god.

↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites:

– No

Notes: In Ori-Oke Iwamimo community, no different loyalty-connection between the elites and the high god exists to the exclusion of other members of the human race.

↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good:

– Yes

Notes: The community holds that the supreme high god is extremely good.

↳ Other feature(s) of supreme high god:

– Yes [specify]: The supreme high god is perfect in splendour and glory. He is the controller of the universe and the creator of all the universe. He reigns supreme over all that transpires within it.

↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world:

– Yes

Notes: The supreme high god has knowledge of all that happens in the world all at the same time without losing facts of happenings in any part of it at anytime. He is omnipresent and omniscient.

↳ The supreme god's knowledge is restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– No

Notes: The community holds that the supreme high god is not restricted to any particular domain of human affairs at anytime.

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– No

Notes: The community does not hold that the supreme high god's knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region:

– Yes

Notes: The community agrees that the high god's knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region.

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region:

– Yes

Notes: The community holds that the supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted outside of the sample region.

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– Yes

Notes: The community holds that the supreme high god can see every mortal everywhere normally visible in public.

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– Yes

Notes: The community holds that the high god can see all mortals everywhere in the dark, at home or in any other location considered hidden to humans.

↳ The supreme high god can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– Yes

Notes: Ori-Oke Iwamimo holds that the supreme high god can see inside the heart or mind including the hidden motives of everyone.

↳ The supreme high god knows your basic character (personal essence):

– Yes

Notes: Ori-Oke Iwamimo holds that the supreme high god knows the basic character and the personal essence of all humans.

↳ The supreme high god knows what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– Yes

Notes: Ori-Oke Iwamimo is clear about their understanding that the supreme high god knows what will happen to all mortals. This includes everything that will happen to all mortals in the future.

↳ The supreme high god has other knowledge of this world:

– Yes [specify]: Ori-Oke Iwamimo holds that every knowledge in this world (the conceivable and inconceivable) is known by the supreme high god.

↳ The supreme high god has deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

Notes: Ori-Oke Iwamimo holds that the supreme high god has deliberate causal efficacy in the world.

↳ The supreme high god can reward:

– Yes

Notes: The community holds that the supreme high god can reward every action of all individuals in the world.

↳ The supreme high god can punish:

– Yes

Notes: The community holds that the supreme high god can punish every action of all individuals in the world.

↳ The supreme high god has indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

Notes: Just as the community holds that the supreme high god has direct causal efficacy in the world, it equally has the belief that the supreme high god has indirect causal efficacy in the world. The supreme high god is seen as either actively controlling the actions or deeds of humans as well as being permissive of their actions at other times. This, he is believed to do so as to make humans accountable for their actions and to draw rewards or punishments for their actions in due course.

↳ The supreme high god exhibits positive emotion:

– Yes

Notes: The supreme high god is held as a mighty being who exhibits positive emotions in his interactions with the human race.

↳ The supreme high god exhibits negative emotion:

– Yes

Notes: The community holds that the supreme high god only exhibits negative emotions to the evils of men. This is usually displayed when he intends to correct or judge such actions. Otherwise, the supreme high god is conceived of as having positive emotions always.

↳ The supreme high god possesses hunger:

– No

Notes: In the strict sense, the community does not conceive of their supreme high god as one who hungers for food or physical nourishment.

↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural beings other than the high god:

– No

Notes: The community does not hold any other supernatural being as being worthy of human worship aside the supreme high god.

↳ The supreme high god possesses/exhibits some other feature:

– Yes [specify]: The features of the supreme high god in Ori-Oke Iwamimo is simply endless and can only be limited to the extent of the conception and capability of each human mind. He is held as being kind, benevolent and gracious among other features among the people of Ori-Oke Iwamimo community.

↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living:

– Yes

Notes: Ori-Oke Iwamimo holds that the supreme high god communicates with the living in several ways using several methods.

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– Yes

Notes: The community holds that the supreme high god communicates with humans in waking and in everyday life.

↳ In dreams:

– Yes

Notes: The community holds that the supreme high god communicates with humans in dreams. The prophets of Ori-Oke Iwamimo especially encounter the high god in dreams always. Their dreams are usually means of receiving divine instructions on various topics or dimensions of human endeavours.

↳ In trance possession:

– Yes

Notes: The community holds that the supreme high god communicates with humans in trances. The prophets of Ori-Oke Iwamimo especially encounter the high god in trances. This is usually a means of receiving divine instructions on various topics or dimensions of human endeavours. They could be half awake or active when having such encounters. When they apply the instructions or suggestions received in the trance, outstanding results usually follow such applications.

↳ Through divination practices:

– Yes

Notes: The form of divination practice deployed in Ori-Oke Iwamimo is prayers to the high god. Through prayers they seek to inquire into the mind of the high god and receive instructions on the way to confront their challenges and fulfil their aspirations..

↳ Only through religious specialists:

– No

Notes: Both the religious specialists and non-specialists approach and seek the guidance of the high god in Ori-Oke Iwamimo. They all have access to the high god but the specialists seem to be more acquainted with the means and methods of securing the attention of the high god.

↳ Only through monarch

– No

Notes: Every member of the community has access to the high god. They are all encouraged to seek the face of the high god and obtain answers to their petitions as individuals.

↳ Other form of communication with living:

– Yes [specify]: The supreme high god speaks to the members of the community through circumstances, in audible voices etc

↳ Previously human spirits are present:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits can be seen:

– No

Notes: The community does not believe that human spirits can be seen physically with the human eye but certain individuals gifted with spiritual powers (prophets and other religious specialists) can see and communicate with human spirits.

↳ Human spirits can be physically felt:

– No

Notes: The community does not believe that human spirits can be felt. However, certain individuals gifted with special powers (prophets and other religious specialists) can feel the presence and perceive the activities of human spirits, especially the human spirits which perpetrate evil.

↳ Previously human spirits have knowledge of this world:

– Yes

Notes: The community holds that previously human spirits have knowledge of this world. Their knowledge is usually restricted to the area they lived and the individuals they knew while they were still alive. Generally, it could be said that their activities are restricted to individuals that were connected to them or their region while they lived.

↳ Human spirits' knowledge restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– Yes

Notes: Ori-Oke Iwamimo holds that human spirits' knowledge is restricted to particular domain of human affairs. Usually, they operate within the scope of their geographical region or their physical area of contact. In rare cases, human spirits, with the aid of some spiritual powers operate outside the scope of their physical contact.

↳ Human spirits' knowledge restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– Yes

Notes: Ori-Oke Iwamimo believes that human spirits' knowledge are restricted to specific areas within the sample region. The exception to this is when human spirits are enabled or aided by the supernatural being to access and process

information outside their area of physical contact.

↳ Human spirits' knowledge unrestricted within the sample region:

– No

Notes: The community holds that human spirits' knowledge is restricted within the sample region

↳ Human spirits' knowledge unrestricted outside of sample region:

– No

Notes: Except when divinely enabled, the community holds that human spirits are totally incapable of knowing anything or accessing information about issues, events and happenings outside of their sample region.

↳ Human spirits can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– No

Notes: The community holds that although human spirits can see everywhere normally visible (in public), they can only do so about objects, humans and events within their vicinity or physical reach.

↳ Human spirits can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– No

Notes: Human spirits of those who are still alive cannot see beyond their reach in the dark. They are indeed limited in their capacity to see beyond their immediate physical environment. However, spirits of those who have exited the realm of human existence but are forced to remain around because of the circumstances surrounding their death can see everywhere within the area of their interest in order to achieve the purpose they have set for themselves. The circumstances of death which forces the spirits of some demised folks to remain around the living include those who were killed violently or those who died before the time they were destined to. They stay around to afflict those who took their lives before exiting their region finally.

↳ Human spirit's can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– No

Notes: Ori-Oke iwamimo community beliefs the human spirit cannot see inside the heart/mind or the hidden motives. However, those who have died but whose spirits still inhabit natural phenomena like trees, water bodies etc have the ability to see inside the heart/mind and detect the hidden motives in the hearts.

↳ Human spirits know your basic character (personal essence):

– No

Notes: Ori-Oke iwamimo community beliefs the human spirits cannot always accurately predict the basic character or personal essence of others. However, those who have died but whose spirits still remain within the human community have the ability to know the basic character (personal essence) of other beings.

↳ Human spirits know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– No

Notes: Ori-Oke iwamimo community beliefs the human spirit cannot what will happen to others or what they will do (future sight). However, those who have died but whose spirits still remain within the human community have the ability to know what will happen to humans and what they will do in the future.

↳ Human spirits have other form(s) of knowledge regarding this world:

– No

Notes: Ori-Oke Iwamimo does not belief that human spirits have other forms of knowledge regarding this world. However, they conceive of the spirits of those who have died but whose spirits still choose to remain within the human community as having other forms of knowing regarding this world. They could tap into the supernatural realm of existence to draw up knowledge not accessible to men. Such knowledge could be used by them to fulfil the desires of their hearts regarding any matter that interests them.

↳ Human spirits have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits can reward:

– Yes

Notes: The community believes that human spirits are agents or part of the complex structure that enforces the law of karma. When a being exercises uprightness and devotion to God, the supreme being ensures they are kept from the wandering evil human spirits. The high god sees to it that they are protected by all means including prompting the prophets to secure them in difficult circumstances.

↳ Human spirits can punish:

– Yes

Notes: Human spirits - inhabiting the prophets - can reward (that is, they could be used to wade off evil from the kind and pious folks). At the same time human spirits (at work in evil persons; dead or alive) could also be used as instruments for punishing humans for wrongdoing.

↳ Human spirits have indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

Notes: Ori-Oke Iwamimo believes that spirits, just like humans could act inadvertently to fulfil the law of karma. While serving this purpose, they are often oblivion of their role in apportioning rewards for both good and evil deeds exercised by humans in the past.

↳ Human spirits have memory of life:

– Yes

Notes: Spirits of living members of the human race usually retain memories of life and are able to build on previous knowledge of events and happenings in such a way that such knowledge affects their future actions. In same vein, spirits of the departed also remember events which they witnessed or partook in while they were living.

↳ Human spirits exhibit positive emotion:

– Yes

Notes: Spirits of living members of the human race are capable of exhibiting positive emotions like kindness, gratitude and honesty. So also spirits of the departed who continue to inhabit spiritual spaces near their previous homes exhibit positive emotions to those who have a pure heart and good motives.

↳ Human spirits exhibit negative emotion:

– Yes

Notes: Spirits of living members of the human race are capable of exhibiting negative emotions like hatred, dishonesty and being vengeful. So also spirits of the departed who continue to inhabit spiritual spaces near their previous homes exhibit negative emotions to those who undertake evil deeds or whose ways are not pure.

↳ Human spirits possess hunger:

– Yes

Notes: Spirits of the living members of the community possess hunger (hunger to meet their nutritional needs and emotional hunger). Spirits of the departed which are in close contact with the people also possess emotional (positive and negative) hunger.

↳ Human spirits possess/exhibit some other feature:

– Yes [specify]: Human spirits may also be benevolent or full of wrath. They may reward or punish wrongdoing. The community also speaks of some human spirits as being very tough and not easy to be cheated.

↳ Human spirits communicate with the living:

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– Yes

Notes: Ori-Oke Iwamimo believes that human spirits (of the dead) communicate with the living as they wake and go about their daily tasks. They also hold that the spirit within each individual being equally suggests to them how to go about their plans and actions. However, many do not understand when such still voice speaks to them from within and so they miss such opportunity to follow their heart thereby avoiding pitfalls in the execution of their plans.

↳ In dreams:

– Yes

Notes: Ori-Oke Iwamimo believes that human spirits (of the dead) communicate with the living through dreams. They also hold that by some supernatural means, human spirits also receive inspirations to undertake certain actions by means of dreaming while sleeping.

↳ In trance possession:

– Yes

Notes: Ori-Oke Iwamimo community believes that human spirits receive supernatural instructions as they fall into trances. They hold that by some supernatural means, human spirits (especially of prophets and other religious specialists) receive inspirations to undertake certain actions by means of trances. This could happen to them under the atmosphere of worship or while carrying out other mundane activities.

↳ Through divination processes:

– Yes

Notes: Ori-Oke Iwamimo community believes that human spirits receive supernatural instructions through divination processes. They do this while praying to the supreme being. They anticipate the response of the supreme being through answers to their prayers or by providing some other type of guidance which would lead to the resolution of the issues for which they sought his face.

↳ Only through specialists:

– No

Notes: Every member of Ori-Oke Iwamimo community could receive some guidance from the spirit realm. They are not restricted to the use of intermediaries (specialists) in receiving guidance from the realm of the supernatural.

↳ Only through monarch:

– No

Notes: Every member of Ori-Oke Iwamimo community could receive some guidance from the spirit realm. They are not entirely dependent on their monarch for this kind of service.

↳ Communicate with living through other means:

– Yes [specify]: There are several other means by which the spirit communicates with members of the community. These includes through the bible, in sermons and general instructions in religious gatherings, through counselling by religious specialists etc

↳ Non-human supernatural beings are present:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings can be seen:

– No

Notes: The non-human supernatural beings present in Ori-Oke Iwamimo cannot be seen by most of the members or people in general. However, when giving the privilege, the prophets and other religious specialists may be made to see them for specific purposes.

↳ These supernatural beings can be physically felt:

– No

Notes: In most cases, the supernatural beings acknowledged in Ori-Oke iwamimo cannot be physically felt. However, in special cases, they make their physical presence felt through some strange incidences like manifesting in the form of a strong wind.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world:

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– No

Notes: Ori-Oke Iwamimo community believes that non-human supernatural beings have unrestricted knowledge in human affairs.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– No

Notes: In Ori-Oke Iwamimo community, the knowledge of non-human supernatural beings is not restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge unrestricted within the sample region:

— Yes

Notes: In Ori-Oke Iwamimo community, non-human supernatural beings have knowledge unrestricted within the sample region.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge unrestricted outside of sample region:

— Yes

Notes: In Ori-Oke Iwamimo community, non-human supernatural beings have knowledge unrestricted outside of the sample region.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

— Yes

Notes: In Ori-Oke iwamimo community, non-human supernatural beings can see humans everywhere normally visible (in public)

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

— Yes

Notes: In Ori-Oke Iwamimo community, non-human supernatural beings can see all humans everywhere (in the dark, at home)

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

— Yes

Notes: In Ori-Oke iwamimo community, non-human supernatural beings can see inside human heart/mind (hidden motives)

↳ Non-human supernatural beings knows your basic character (personal essence):

— Yes

Notes: In Ori-Oke Iwamimo community, non-human supernatural beings know the basic character (personal essence) of all human beings

↳ Non-human supernatural beings know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

— Yes

Notes: In Ori-Oke Iwamimo community, non-human supernatural beings know what will happen to human beings and what they will do (future sight)

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have other knowledge of this world:

– Yes [specify]: The community holds that non-human supernatural beings have other knowledge of this world. The knowledge they possess includes all information about previous generations and future generations of beings. They also have vast knowledge regarding things yet to be conceived by human beings.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

Notes: As agents of the supreme being, non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world. This is because they share in the attributes of the supreme being which they represent in all things.

↳ These supernatural beings can reward:

– Yes

Notes: The supernatural beings can reward. They do this on the behalf of the supreme being they represent in the human community.

↳ These supernatural beings can punish:

– Yes

Notes: The supernatural beings can punish. They do this on the behalf of the supreme being they represent in the human community.

↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

Notes: The community beliefs that by virtue of their dominance in the spiritual realm, they indirectly regulate retribution. Supernatural beings monitor the actions of all humans and ensure justice for every action taken. The result is that for all charitable or non-charitable actions undertaken by mortals they receive a reward justifiable to their actions.

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion:

– Yes

Notes: The community hold that the supernatural beings exhibit positive emotions.

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion:

– Yes

Notes: The community holds that the supernatural beings have the capacity to exhibit negative emotions.

↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger:

– Yes

Notes: The type of hunger the supernatural beings possess is that for righteousness. They also have a hunger to reward (for charitable deeds) or punish (for non-charitable deeds) humans for their actions.

↳ These supernatural beings possess/exhibit some other feature:

– Yes [specify]: The supernatural beings possess or exhibit other features which includes protection for humans, upholding justice, encouraging humans to obey divine instructions, ensuring the kingdom of the supernatural being is progressing among the human race etc

↳ Mixed human-divine beings are present:

– No

Notes: The notion of mixed human-divine beings is not present in the community.

↳ Does the religious group possess a variety of supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Organized by kinship based on a family model:

– No

Notes: The variety of supernatural beings present in the theology of Ori-Oke iwamimo community is not organized by kinship or based on family model.

↳ Organized hierarchically:

– Yes

Notes: The supernatural beings recognized in the community are perceived to be in hierarchical order.

↳ Power of beings is domain specific:

– No

Notes: The community does not rank the supernatural beings based on the domain they are perceived to function or reside

↳ Other organization for pantheon:

– No

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– Yes

↳ There is supernatural monitoring of prosocial norm adherence in particular:

Prosocial norms are norms that enhance cooperation among members of the group, including obviously “moral” or “ethical” norms, but also extending to norms concerning honouring contracts and oaths, providing hospitality, coming to mutual aid in emergencies, etc.

– Yes

Notes: The community believes that supernatural monitoring of prosocial norm adherence is present among them.

↳ Supernatural beings care about taboos:

– Yes

↳ Food:

– No

Notes: The community does not hold taboos regarding foods.

↳ Sacred space(s):

– Yes

Notes: A space like the church is held as sacred. Therefore, some activities are not permitted in the church auditorium.

↳ Sacred object(s):

– Yes

Notes: The bell used by the first monarch of the community was held as a sacred object. Some other objects used during spiritual undertakings in the act of worship are also considered sacred. These include wooden swords, flags hoisted for spiritual purposes etc

↳ Supernatural beings care about other:

– No

Notes: The community does not have a bogus structure of taboos or forbidden practices. They shun all antisocial activities and actions that break the bond of love among the members of the community.

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of coreligionists:

– Yes

Notes: The killing of any human being is forbidden in the community.

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other religions:

– Yes

Notes: The killing of any human being is forbidden in the community.

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other polities:

– Yes

Notes: The killing of any human being is forbidden in the community.

↳ Supernatural beings care about sex:

– Yes

↳ Adultery:

– Yes

Notes: Adultery is forbidden in Ori-Oke Iwamimo community.

↳ Incest:

– Yes

Notes: Incest is forbidden in Ori-Oke Iwamimo community

↳ Other sexual practices:

– Yes [specify]: Pre-marital sex is also forbidden in Ori-Oke Iwamimo community. Only sexual relations between married heterosexual partners is permitted in the community.

↳ Supernatural beings care about lying:

– Yes

Notes: In Ori-Oke Iwamimo, supernatural beings care about lying. They abhor the practice and are reckoned as stipulating that all liars shall be damned in eternal fire.

↳ Supernatural beings care about honouring oaths:

– Yes

Notes: The community holds oaths as pronouncements that must be fulfilled.

↳ Supernatural beings care about laziness:

– Yes

Notes: Laziness is frowned at in the community.

↳ Supernatural beings care about sorcery:

– Yes

Notes: Sorcery is forbidden in the community. It was one of the major issues the community dealt with in its formative years. Those perceived to be witches and wizards were often identified and severely dealt with. They were often made to renounce their membership of the witchcraft covens or cults and words obtained from them that they had abandoned witchcraft and sorcery.

↳ Supernatural beings care about non-lethal fighting:

– Yes

Notes: Fighting of any sort is forbidden in the community.

↳ Supernatural beings care about shirking risk:

– Yes

Notes: In the community, risks are meant to be reasonably approached and tasks involving risks carefully executed. The community holds that supernatural beings have endowed their members with the wherewithal to manage risks and execute all assignments given them. They frown at people who refuse to undertake activities involving minimal risks. Such people are tagged as slothful and lazy.

↳ Supernatural beings care about disrespecting elders:

– Yes

Notes: The community does not take kindly any act of disrespect to elders.

↳ Supernatural beings care about gossiping:

– Yes

Notes: Gossiping is frowned at in Ori-Oke Iwamimo community.

↳ Supernatural beings care about property crimes:

– Yes

Notes: The community has zero tolerance for crimes.

↳ Supernatural beings care about proper ritual observance:

– Yes

Notes: The community holds that proper ritual observance is a necessary condition for answered prayers. So they place emphasis on proper ritual observance.

↳ Supernatural beings care about performance of rituals:

– Yes

Notes: The community holds that supernatural beings care about performance of rituals

↳ Supernatural beings care about conversion of non-religionists:

– Yes

Notes: Though the community believes that the supernatural beings care about conversion of non-religionists, they do not vigorously go out proselytising non-members. They allow non-members make the choice to join them. They are rather not aggressive to win non-members over.

↳ Supernatural beings care about economic fairness:

– Yes

Notes: The community hold members responsible to use just measures in marketing their goods and to embrace honesty and transparency in their trade, commerce and economic activities.

↳ Supernatural beings care about personal hygiene:

– Yes

Notes: The community holds the view that supernatural beings care about personal hygiene. They encourage individuals in the community to maintain personal hygiene.

↳ Supernatural beings care about other:

– Yes [specify]: The community believes that supernatural beings care about everything that will engender peace, progress and development among the people. They hold that supernatural beings care about sharing of their possessions with those who lack and giving a helping hand to those who need their help among others.

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– Yes

↳ Is the cause or agent of supernatural punishment known:

– Yes

↳ Done only by high god:

– No

Notes: The high god metes out supernatural punishment but also uses other beings to carry out the task as he wills.

↳ Done by many supernatural beings:

– Yes

Notes: All supernatural beings involved in executing punishment for wrongdoing do so under the coordination of the supreme being. Some of them are angels and other beings in heavenly places.

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle:

– Yes

Notes: The impersonal cause-effect principle is also employed by the supreme being to execute punishment on humanity for wrongdoing.

↳ Done by other entities or through other means [specify]

– Yes

Notes: In the community, nature and environmental forces are also viewed as an agent for executing punishment on humans for wrongdoing.

↳ Is the reason for supernatural punishment known:

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:

– Yes

Notes: The community holds that in some cases, supernatural punishment is done to enforce religious ritual-devotion or adherence.

↳ Done to enforce group norms:

– Yes

Notes: The community believes that supernatural punishment is also meted out to enforce adherence to group norms. When some individuals are punished for flouting group norms, it serves as a deterrent to others who may want to neglect such norms in future.

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness:

– Yes

Notes: The community holds that supernatural punishments are meted out in some instances to inhibit selfishness and rather encourage selflessness.

↳ Done randomly:

– No

Notes: The community does not believe that punishments are executed randomly. They are usually brought about for specific purposes and to discourage specific acts.

↳ Other [specify]

– Yes

Notes: The community holds that supernatural punishments are at times meted out to show the almightiness of the supreme being to humble the proud, arrogant and merciless individuals.

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in the afterlife:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural punishments in the afterlife are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: Supernatural punishments in the afterlife are highly emphasised in Ori-Oke Iwamimo community.

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of mild sensory displeasure:

– No

Notes: The community holds that punishment in the afterlife consists of extreme sensory displeasure.

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of extreme sensory displeasure:

– Yes

Notes: The community holds that punishment in the afterlife consists of extreme sensory displeasure.

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation as an inferior life form:

– No

Notes: Reincarnation as an inferior life form is not a form of punishment conceived in the theology of Ori-Oke Iwamimo community.

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation in an inferior realm:

– No

Notes: Reincarnation in an inferior realm in the afterlife is not a form of punishment considered possible in Ori_Oke Iwamimo community.

↳ Other [specify]

– Yes

Notes: The community holds that the fire prepared for evil doers in hell is unquenchable. They will also be bitten by venomous reptiles, insects and other dangerous animals.

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in this lifetime:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural punishments in this life are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: In Ori-Oke Iwamimo community, supernatural punishments in this life are highly emphasized.

↳ Punishment in this life consists of bad luck:

– Yes

Notes: The community holds that people who are being punished for wrongdoing could experience bad luck in their endeavours.

↳ Punishment in this life consists of political failure:

– Yes

Notes: The community reasons that political failures are due to the many offenses or wrongdoing of humanity. They call on citizens to repent of their wrongdoings so the supernatural could usher in times of refreshing and political stability.

↳ Punishment in this life consists of defeat in battle:

– Yes

Notes: In Ori-Oke Iwamimo community, defeats in battle are sometimes seen as punishments for the wrongs committed by individuals or societies.

↳ Punishment in this life consists of crop failure or bad weather:

– No

Notes: As a riparian community, the people holds that the evil deeds of men bring about negative consequences which include poor catch in the rivers and the Atlantic ocean.

↳ Punishment in this life consists of disaster on journeys.

– Yes

Notes: The community holds that disaster on journeys could be a form of punishment in this life.

↳ Punishment in this life consists of mild sensory displeasure:

– Yes

Notes: According to Ori-Oke iwamimo community, sensory displeasures (mild or extreme) could be results of punishment in this life.

↳ Punishment in this life consists of extreme sensory displeasure:

– Yes

Notes: According to Ori-Oke iwamimo community, sensory displeasures (mild or extreme) could be results of punishment in this life.

↳ Punishment in this life consists of sickness or illness:

– Yes

Notes: The community holds that sickness or illness could be a form of punishment in this life.

↳ Punishment in this life consists of impaired reproduction:

– Yes

Notes: The community holds that impaired reproduction could be a form of punishment in this life.

↳ Punishment in this life consists of bad luck visited on descendants:

– Yes

Notes: The community believes that bad luck could be visited on descendants as punishments in this life for the wrongdoing of parents.

↳ Other [specify]

– Yes

Notes: Ori-Oke iwamimo community holds that misfortunes and a plethora of evil occurrences could manifest as punishments for the wrongdoing of individuals and communities. This includes job losses, barrenness, disability, strange and unexplainable catastrophic events like the Covid-19 pandemic etc

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– Yes

↳ Is the cause/purpose of supernatural rewards known:

– Yes

↳ Done only by high god:

– No

Notes: The community holds that the high god bestows rewards personally. However, he also delegates other beings to bestow rewards on his behalf.

↳ Done by many supernatural beings:

– Yes

Notes: The community believes that the supernatural beings who bestow rewards only do so as agents of the high god.

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle:

– Yes

Notes: The community holds that sometimes, the impersonal cause-effect principle is used by the high god to distribute rewards to deserving individuals.

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:

– Yes

Notes: Ori-Oke Iwamimo believes that rewards are sometimes given to deserving individuals for the purpose of enforcing religious ritual-devotional adherence. When an individual has been seen to have obtained rewards for past ritual devotion, it has a capacity to motivate others to follow in the footsteps of the recipient of the reward.

↳ Done to enforce group norms:

– Yes

Notes: The community holds that rewards are given in some instances to enforce group norms. When an individual has been seen to have obtained rewards for keeping group norms, it has a capacity to motivate others to follow in the footsteps of the recipient of the reward.

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness:

– Yes

Notes: The community believes that there are instances when rewards are given to inhibit selfishness. When an individual has been seen to have obtained rewards for exhibiting selfless actions, it has a capacity to motivate others to follow in the footsteps of the recipient of the reward.

↳ Done randomly:

– No

Notes: Ori-Oke Iwamimo does not believe that rewards are given out randomly. The community holds that there are definite reasons why people are identified for the purpose of obtaining rewards.

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in the afterlife:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural rewards in the afterlife are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: Supernatural rewards in the afterlife are highly emphasized in the community. The prospect of a reward in the afterlife usually serves as a motivating factor to many to continue to exhibit good deeds.

- ↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of mild sensory pleasure:
– Yes
Notes: According to Ori-Oke iwamimo community, individuals who deserve it would be rewarded with sensory pleasures (mild or extreme) in the afterlife.
- ↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of extreme sensory pleasure:
– Yes
Notes: Notes: According to Ori-Oke iwamimo community, individuals who deserve it would be rewarded with sensory pleasures (mild or extreme) in the afterlife.
- ↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of eternal happiness:
– Yes
Notes: Ori-Oke Iwamimo community holds that individuals who lived a life of obedience will be rewarded with eternal happiness in the afterlife.
- ↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of reincarnation as a superior life form:
– No
Notes: The community does not hold the doctrine of reincarnation.
- ↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of reincarnation in a superior realm:
– No
Notes: The community does not hold the doctrine of reincarnation.
- ↳ Other [specify]
– Yes
Notes: The community holds that rewards in the afterlife will take several forms. For example, many people will reign over kingdoms, others will be in the presence of the high god constantly while some will wear crowns of great value.
- ↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in this lifetime:
– Yes
- ↳ Supernatural rewards in this life are highly emphasized by the religious group:
– Yes
Notes: Supernatural rewards in this life are highly emphasized in the community.
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of good luck:
– Yes
Notes: In Ori-Oke Iwamimo community, good luck is usually seen as a manifestation of

rewards from the supreme being in this life.

Reward in this life consists of political success or power:

– Yes

Notes: Though the community does not covet political power, it holds that peace in the polity and political stability are rewards for people who honour the supreme being in this life.

Reward in this life consists of success in battle:

– Yes

Notes: Although the community does not engage in military campaigns or other forms of combat, it holds that life itself is a battlefield. As such, success over illnesses, in examinations and other human endeavours are seen as rewards in this life.

Reward in this life consists of peace or social stability:

– Yes

Notes: Peace and social stability are seen as rewards in this life in the community.

Reward in this life consists of healthy crops or good weather:

– Yes

Notes: Though the community does not cultivate the land significantly, it sees success in the economic activities of her members as rewards in this life.

Reward in this life consists of success on journeys:

– Yes

Notes: Success on journeys are held as rewards in this life in the community.

Reward in this life consists of mild sensory pleasure:

– Yes

Notes: The community holds that rewards in this life consists of mild sensory pleasures.

Reward in this life consists of extreme sensory pleasure:

– Yes

Notes: The community holds that rewards in this life consists of extreme sensory pleasures.

Reward in this life consists of enhanced health:

– Yes

Notes: Ori-Oke Iwamimo holds that enhanced health conditions are indications of

rewards in this life.

↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced reproductive success:

– Yes

Notes: The community sees enhanced reproductive success as a reward to people in this life.

↳ Reward in this life consists of fortune visited on descendants:

– Yes

Notes: The community sees fortunes visited on descendants as a form of reward to parents in this life.

↳ Other [specify]

– Yes

Notes: Several pleasant outcomes in personal and community life are seen as rewards in this life. These include prosperity in business, having a settled home, raising well mannered children among others.

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present:

– Yes

↳ Is the messiah's whereabouts or time of coming known?

– Yes

↳ Alive, identified:

– Yes

Notes: The community belief in Jesus Christ (messiah). They hold that he once came into the world, he died, was buried and resurrected on the third day. They believe that he is now alive and is preparing the saints a place in his kingdom.

↳ Is the messiah's purpose known:

– Yes

Notes: They hold that the messiah's purpose is to come and save humanity from eternal separation from the high god.

↳ Messiah is a political figure who restores political rule:

– No

Notes: They hold that their messiah is interested in spiritual restoration and not political restoration.

↳ Messiah is a priestly figure who restores religious traditions:

– Yes

Notes: The community holds that the messiah is a priestly figure who restores religious traditions

↳ Other purpose:

– Yes [specify]: The community believe that the messiah came to save the lost, to lift the burden and yoke of oppression from all of humanity.

Is an eschatology present:

– Yes

↳ Eschaton in this lifetime:

– Yes

Notes: The community holds that at the end of this world several events will take place. Those who have lived well will receive rewards while those who were evil in their ways will enter eternal damnation.

↳ Eschaton at specified time in future:

– No

Notes: No specific time is allotted to the eschaton as believed upon by the community.

↳ Eschaton at unspecified time in near future:

– Yes

Notes: Though the community holds that the time of eschaton is near, no one knows the exact time. Moreover, according to the bible they believe in, it was said by those who lived over one thousand years ago that eschaton was going to happen soon or in their lifetime but it never did. The community is still awaiting the eschaton.

↳ Eschaton at unspecified time in distant future:

– No

Notes: Though the eschaton is believed upon as an event in the future, the community does not estimate the time of its happening to the distant future.

↳ Eschaton at some other time:

– No

Notes: The community holds that the time for eschaton is in the near future.

↳ Adherents need to perform specific tasks to bring about World's end:

– No

Notes: The community holds that the eschaton is in the near future. They need not undertake any significant tasks for this to happen.

↳ Divine judgment event:

– Yes

Notes: The community holds that there shall be divine judgement in the events around the end time.

↳ Restoration of the world:

– Yes

Notes: The community holds that the events of the eschaton would bring about a restoration of the world to its original state of peace and tranquillity.

↳ Start of a new temporal cycle:

– No

Notes: The community holds that the events of the eschaton would signify the start of a permanent cycle.

↳ Establishment of a new political system:

– Yes

Notes: The community holds that theocracy which they practice would be the new form of governance in the whole world and under a single king; Jesus Christ.

↳ Establishment of a new religious system:

– Yes

Notes: The community holds that theocracy which they practice would be the new religious system in the whole world and under a single king; Jesus Christ.

↳ Will anyone survive the eschaton:

– Yes

↳ All religious in-group members will survive the eschaton:

– No

Notes: The community holds that those who are raptured during the appearance of the messiah will be safe from the terror of the antichrist.

↳ A subset of religion in-group members will survive the eschaton:

– No

Notes: The community holds that the eschaton is not easy to survive.

↳ All members of the sample region will survive the eschaton:

– No

Notes: The community holds that the eschaton is not easy to survive.

↳ Everyone in the world will survive the eschaton:

– No

Notes: The community holds that the eschaton is not easy to survive.

↳ Other survival condition:

– Yes [specify]: The community holds that those who fail to accept the mark of the antichrist have a chance to survive eschaton.

Norms and Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: The community prescribes social norms to her members. They do not expect any member to steal, kill, tell lies, disobey the high god among other norms.

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:

– No

Notes: The community believes in morality. Its conventions are drawn from its moral standards.

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Honesty / trustworthiness / integrity:

– Yes

Notes: The community places high value on honesty, trustworthiness and integrity.

↳ Courage (in battle):

– Yes

Notes: The community teaches her members to be courageous. Though they do not engage in physical battles, they proclaim that life is a battlefield where the forces of good and evil are ever in contest for the souls of humans. Each member is encouraged to fight a good spiritual warfare in a bid to make it to the blissful eternal afterlife (heaven).

↳ Courage (generic):

– Yes

Notes: The community teaches her members to face life with courage if they want to be successful in their endeavours.

↳ Compassion / empathy / kindness / benevolence:

– Yes

Notes: Ori-Oke Iwamimo emphasises the need for her members to display compassion, empathy, kindness and benevolence in all their engagements.

↳ Mercy / forgiveness / tolerance:

– Yes

Notes: Mercy, forgiveness and tolerance are key attributes the community teaches her members.

↳ Generosity / charity:

– Yes

Notes: The community encourages her members to uphold the virtues of generosity and charity.

↳ Selflessness / selfless giving:

– Yes

Notes: Ori-Oke Iwamimo reiterates the need for her members to keep being selfless and be committed to selfless giving.

↳ Righteousness / moral rectitude:

– Yes

Notes: The community upholds righteousness and moral rectitude. The need for members to inculcate these attributes is always emphasised.

↳ Ritual purity / ritual adherence / abstention from sources of impurity:

– Yes

Notes: Ori-Oke Iwamimo teaches her members to maintain ritual purity, ritual adherence and to abstain from sources of impurity.

↳ Respectfulness / courtesy:

– Yes

Notes: The community encourages members to be respectful and give due courtesy to people deserving of it.

↳ Familial obedience / filial piety:

– Yes

Notes: The community teaches her members to to maintain familial obedience and filial piety.

↳ Fidelity / loyalty:

– Yes

Notes: Ori-Oke iwamimo emphasises fidelity and loyalty among her members.

↳ Cooperation:

– Yes

Notes: The community encourages cooperation among her members. They are taught the power that cooperation brings to accomplishing collective goals.

↳ Independence / creativity / freedom:

– Yes

Notes: The community teaches a balance between independence, creativity and freedom. Members are taught to exercise these views but be mindful of the overall goals of the community and the other groups they belong.

↳ Moderation / frugality:

– Yes

Notes: Ori-Oke iwamimo encourages moderation and frugality among her members.

↳ Forbearance / fortitude / patience:

– Yes

Notes: The community upholds forbearance, fortitude and patience and encourages members to exercise these virtues.

↳ Diligence / self-discipline / excellence:

– Yes

Notes: The community teaches members the need to exercise diligence, self-discipline and excellence in their undertakings

↳ Assertiveness / decisiveness / confidence / initiative:

– Yes

Notes: Ori-Oke iwamimo encourages members to be assertive, decisive, confident and to demonstrate initiative in executing daily or special tasks assigned to them.

↳ Strength (physical):

– Yes

Notes: The community teaches members to deploy their strength in order to fully maximise their potentials and accomplish their tasks and roles effectively.

↳ Power / status / nobility:

– Yes

Notes: The community teaches the proper use of power to achieve the overall objectives of the society. They believe that status and nobility should not be used to cheat others but to lift humanity.

↳ Humility / modesty:

– Yes

Notes: Ori-Oke Iwamimo emphasises on humility and modesty among her members.

↳ Contentment / serenity / equanimity:

– Yes

Notes: The community teaches the virtues of contentment, serenity and equanimity among her members.

↳ Joyfulness / enthusiasm / cheerfulness:

– Yes

Notes: The community encourages members to keep being joyful in hope be enthusiastic and remain cheerful at all times.

↳ Optimism / hope:

– Yes

Notes: Optimism and hope are two important virtues embraced in Ori-Oke Iwamimo community.

↳ Gratitude / thankfulness:

– Yes

Notes: The community admonishes her members to always be full of gratitude and thankfulness to the supreme being and others who show benevolence to them.

↳ Reverence / awe / wonder:

– Yes

Notes: The community asks members to show reverence, awe and wonder to the supreme being at all times

↳ Faith / belief / trust / devotion:

– Yes

Notes: Faith, belief, trust and devotion are key virtues the community holds as debts owed the supreme being. They ask members to be full of each of these virtues at all times

↳ Wisdom / understanding:

– Yes

Notes: The community requests members to be full of wisdom and understanding as they conduct themselves around in the course of their daily activities.

↳ Discernment / intelligence:

– Yes

Notes: The community asks members to demonstrate the virtue of discernment and to grow their power of intelligence so as to get the best out of life.

↳ Beauty / attractiveness:

– Yes

Notes: The community understands that beauty and attractiveness are very good but do not place premium over them above good character and a positive spirit.

↳ Cleanliness (physical) / orderliness:

– Yes

Notes: Ori-Oke iwamimo upholds physical cleanliness of their members and their environment. The community also places emphasis on orderliness in private and public life.

↳ Other important virtues advocated by the religious group:

– Yes [specify]: The community teaches members the importance of having team spirit, being vigilant and watchful and prioritising the safety of everyone around them.

Practices

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– No

Notes: There is no doctrine of celibacy or sexual abstinence in Ori-Oke Iwamimo community

Does membership in this religious group require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence):

– Yes

↳ Monogamy (males):

– No

Notes: Male members are not required to practice monogamy in the community.

↳ Monogamy (females):

– Yes

Notes: Female members are required to practice monogamy in the community

↳ Other sexual constraints (males):

– Yes

Notes: No one is permitted to have sexual intercourse with an unmarried person or with the spouse of another person.

↳ Other sexual constraints (females):

– Yes

Notes: No one is permitted to have sexual intercourse with an unmarried person or with the spouse of another person.

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– No

Notes: Castration is no a condition for membership in Ori-Oke Iwamimo community.

Does membership in this religious group require fasting:

– Yes

Notes: There are times when members of the community are encouraged to fast and pray in Ori-Oke Iwamimo.

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods):

– No

Notes: Membership of Ori-Oke Iwamimo does not require forgone food opportunities.

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations:

– No

Notes: Membership in this religious group does not require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations

Does membership in this religious group require painful physical positions or transitory

painful wounds:

– No

Notes: Membership in this religious group does not require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds.

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Notes: Membership in this religious group does not require sacrifice of adults

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Notes: Membership in this religious group does not require sacrifice of children.

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– No

Notes: Membership in this religious group does not require self-sacrifice or suicide.

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of property/valuable items:

– No

Notes: Membership in this religious group does not require sacrifice of property or valuable items.

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.):

– Yes

Notes: Membership in this religious group requires sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.)

Does membership in this religious group require physical risk taking:

– No

Notes: Physical risk taking is not a membership requirement of this religious group.

Does membership in this religious group require accepting ethical precepts:

– Yes

Notes: Membership in this religious group requires accepting ethical precepts.

Does membership in this religious group require marginalization by out-group members:

– No

Notes: Membership in this religious group does not require marginalization by out-group members.

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household):

– No

Notes: Membership in this religious group does not require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household). Families may only choose to pray among themselves to fight a course involving anyone of them to complement the efforts of the community on a larger scale.

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

I.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale “ceremonies” and “festivals.”

– Yes

↳ On average, for large-scale rituals how many participants gather in one location:

– Number of participants: 50

Notes: At least fifty members present in the community at every meeting time gather to pray and fellowship in the community church twice daily. The number could be significantly more depending on the number of people within the community during each prayer time.

↳ What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):

Performances here refers to large-scale rituals.

– Average interval [hours]: 12

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:

Orthodoxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are interpreted in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper interpretation, etc.

– No

Notes: There are no orthodoxy checks done during meeting times in the community.

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:

Orthopraxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are performed in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper procedure, etc.

– No

Notes: There are no orthopraxy checks done during meeting times in the community.

↳ Does participation entail synchronic practices:

– No

Notes: Synchronic practices are seldom witnessed during religious meetings in the community.

↳ Is there use of intoxicants:

– No

Notes: Intoxicants are never used during religious meetings in the community.

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present:

E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

– Yes

↳ Tattoos/scarification:

– No

Notes: Tattoos or scarification are not part of religious practices in the community.

↳ Circumcision:

– Yes

Notes: Male infants in the community are usually circumcised on or before the eighth day in the community.

↳ Food taboos:

– No

Notes: Food taboos are not a part of religious practices in the community.

↳ Hair:

– No

Notes: There are no strict moderation around the hair styles members wear in the community. Generally, male members keep a low cut while females may braid or style their hair moderately as it pleases them.

↳ Dress:

– No

Notes: There are no regulations regarding the dressing of members in this community. Ori-Oke Iwamimo is the only one of the four major theocratic communities in Ilajeland which does not subscribe to the use of prayer garments.

↳ Ornaments:

– No

Notes: There is no strict requirement on the use of ornaments in religious practice in the community.

↳ Archaic ritual language:

– Yes

Notes: Members, especially the religious specialists use archaic language (glossolalia) in the community.

↳ Other:

– Yes [specify]: The religious specialists in the community perform interventions as enabled by the supreme being while conducting religious meetings in the community. They proffer spiritual solutions to spiritually decerned issues facing members as they are enabled by the high god.

Does the group employ fictive kinship terminology:

– Yes

↳ Fictive kinship terminology universal:

– Yes

Notes: The members of the community all refer to themselves as children of Ori-Oke Iwamimo. By this, they refer to themselves as originating from the community though in real sense many of them are from other villages in and around Ilajeland.

↳ Fictive kinship terminology widespread:

– Yes

Notes: The members of the community all refer to themselves as children of Ori-Oke Iwamimo. By this, they refer to themselves as originating from the community though in real sense many of them are from other villages in and around Ilajeland. They call themselves "omo Ori-Oke iwamimo". This means children indigenous to the community. This is in spite the fact that not all of them hail from the community.

↳ Fictive kinship terminology employed but uncommon:

– No

Notes: Fictive kinship terminology is employed and common in the community.

Society and Institutions

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– A band

Notes: Ori-Oke iwamimo is located within an area belonging to Mahin clan in Ilajeland. The Ilaje people affirm that they are of the Yoruba stock, one of the largest ethnic groups in Nigeria.

Welfare

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized famine relief:

– No

Notes: Ori-Oke Iwamimo does not provide institutional famine relief. The community however provides aid to people who need relief within their population.

Is famine relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Notes: Famine relief is not available to the group's adherents through any institution external to the group.

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized poverty relief:

– Yes

Notes: The community in former times operated an effective cooperative society which assisted members set up businesses and or equipped them with means of expanding already established businesses.

Is poverty relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Notes: Poverty relief is not available to the group's adherents through any institution external to the group.

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm:

– No

Notes: The religious group does not provide institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm. However, the community steps in to render support to families which are unable to take care of their elderly or infirm.

Is institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Notes: Institutionalised care for the elderly and infirm is not available to the group's adherents through an institution other than the religious group.

Education

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– Yes

Notes: The community built a primary school within the first decade of its establishment for the purpose of educating their children.

↳ Is formal education restricted to religious professionals:

– No

↳ Is such education open to both males and females:

– Yes

Notes: Education in the schools founded by the community is open to both male and female pupils.

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

– No

Notes: The community operated and ran the school by itself. However, government support has since been made available to the school. This makes the school to come under the control of the government.

Bureaucracy

Do the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

– No

Notes: There is no strict bureaucracy within the group which members interact with. However, there are committees and statutory bodies saddled with some responsibilities towards ensuring compliance with group norms. These groups do not have the characteristics of red tapism like most bureaucracies.

Do the group's adherents interact with other institutional bureaucracies:

– Yes

Notes: The group's adherents interact with institutional bureaucracies outside the community on personal grounds. They do this when attempting to access government/corporate programmes and facilities. These interactions could be in the form of obtaining a bank facility, accessing public services from government agencies, departments and institutions.

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– No

Notes: The community does not provide public food storage.

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Notes: Public food storage is not provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group.

Does the religious group in question provide water management (irrigation, flood control):

– No

Notes: The religious group does not officially provide water management (irrigation, flood control) to her members.

Is water management provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Notes: The community does not access water management provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group.

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

– No

Notes: The community does not provide transportation infrastructure.

Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Notes: Transportation infrastructure is not made available to the group's adherents by any institution other than the religious group itself.

Taxation

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

– No

Notes: The community does not levy taxes or tithes on members. It however appeals to them to make contributions to specifically meet some needs when there is a community project to be undertaken.

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The government takes taxes from members of the community for the provision of public

utilities.

Enforcement

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– No

Notes: The religious group does not provide an institutionalised police force though it has its internal crime prevention strategies. The cherubim band and youth group within the community do their bit to ensure public peace is maintained.

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized police force provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The groups adherents interact with the Nigerian Police Force when the need arises for it.

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– No

Notes: The religious group does not provide institutional judges. However, there are quasi judicial functions undertaken by community elders towards resolving disputes between members of the community.

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized judicial system provided by an an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Rather than take laws into their hands, the group or members adopt the option of involving the judicial system in resolving disputes between them and non-members of the community..

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

– Yes

Do the institutionalized punishments include execution:

– No

Notes: The community does not execute members for any form of offence or anti-social behaviour.

Do the institutionalized punishments include exile:

– Yes

Notes: In rare cases the community may consider excommunicating members. In cases like this, such members could be asked to vacate the community.

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include corporal punishments:

– Yes

Notes: Members under the burden of punishments may be asked to weed overgrown grass or do some other tedious jobs in the interest of the community.

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include ostracism:

– Yes

Notes: Ostracism is considered as punishment for members in extreme cases.

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include seizure of property:

– No

Notes: The community does not practice the seizure of members' properties for any reason.

Are the group's adherents subject to institutionalized punishment enforced by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Notes: No institution except the government is empowered by law to punish members of the community. When required, government regulations must be followed in giving out punishments to members or other citizens as the case may be.

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

– No

Notes: The community does not have a formal legal code.

Are the group's adherents subject to a formal legal code provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The group's adherents are subject to the Nigerian legal code.

Warfare

Does religious group in question possess an institutionalized military:

– No

Notes: The religious group does not possess institutionalised military.

Do the group's adherents participate in an institutionalized military provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Members of the community are free to join the Nigerian Military if they so desire.

Are the group's adherents protected by or subject to an institutionalized military provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The group's adherents are protected by and subject to the Nigerian Military.

Written Language

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

– No

Notes: The religious group does not possess its own distinct written language. The Yoruba language is in use in the community.

Is a non-religion-specific written language available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The Yoruba language is the first language used in the community. English language is also spoken among the youths and educated members of the community.

Is a non-religion-specific written language used by the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Yoruba language is used for writing purposes among the people.

Calendar

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

– No

Notes: The religious group does not possess a formal calendar.

Is a formal calendar provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The religious group uses the Gregorian calendar.

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– No

Notes: The religious group buys most of their food from markets as they do not have enough land for crop production being a coastal settlement.

Is food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Notes: Members of the community buy their food from markets around them. No formal institution meets their food needs.

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